

AGRICULTURAL SCIENCES

MONITORING OF AGRICULTURAL LAND CONDITIONS

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Abstract

Project Goal: To create a program for small flying devices (drones) to determine the area of weeds in agricultural fields based on color and length.

Tasks:

1. Become familiar with the literature on the use of chemical pesticides.
2. Become familiar with existing monitoring technologies.

Hypothesis: Creating a program for early monitoring of the level of weed contamination of agricultural land by plants will help increase yields.

Novelty: In creating a draft program for monitoring agricultural land, a new, improved drone model with a built-in camera and a sprayer was proposed for detecting weeds and then pollinating them with herbicides to regulate crop growth.

Research phases: bibliographic analysis of literature and internet material; writing a program algorithm; creating a drone model; conducting an experiment: scanning weeds for color; analyzing the experiment.

Degree of autonomy: in the implementation and creation of the project program, the student was assisted by his/her supervisor and by teachers of robotics and programming.

Conclusions:

1. A program to detect weeds based on color and height using small aircraft will significantly reduce the amount of herbicides used and lower the cost of their application.
2. Reducing the amount of chemicals sprayed will reduce contamination of soils and groundwater with hazardous substances.
3. A small aircraft allows spraying at low altitudes, reducing the contact area of chemical compounds with natural ecosystems.
- fourth. Early detection of plant diseases will contribute to higher yields

Practical implications: An improved crop monitoring program can be proposed as a way to monitor and control weeds

Objective: to create a program for small flying vehicles (drones) to determine the area of agricultural land weed infestation.

Relevance: Weeds are a serious problem for all crops, including forage crops. Approximately 73% of weed species in cropping systems are not local [1]. On average, because of weeds, diseases and pests in Kazakhstan about 20% of grain yield is lost annually, but in some years underharvest can reach 50% or more, although the species composition of pests is not so numerous. For example, in Burabay district of Akmola region in spring wheat crops the most harmful weeds are oats, bristlegrass, field bindweed, bristle thistle, field thistle, creeping vetch, white crowberry, pickleweed and other weeds [2].

Today, inappropriate weed control damages the environment, leading to an overuse of herbicides, thereby upsetting the natural balance of nature.

Keywords: agroculture, weed, monitoring, code, machine vision, crop, camera, soil pollution, farmer, camera, wheat, drone, height color, algorithm, python

1.1 Methods for monitoring phytosanitary status of fields.

For successful weed control it is necessary to carry out annual accounting of the weed infestation of the fields. Evaluation of weediness of crops is carried out on the basis of data from space and ground-based monitoring, and is timed to the period of maximum growth and development of crops [3].

Drones are rightfully considered the most effective and mobile tool for collecting data on the condition of crops. Usually they are launched at a height of 100-300 meters above the field, which makes the images more detailed than those of satellites. The speed of these devices is also remarkable - a drone covers 2.5 thousand hectares per day. The low imaging altitude and high resolution of the picture make it possible to create a map on which you can distinguish the crop

from the weeds. In some cases, it is even possible to identify a particular variety of pest plant and select the optimal type of herbicide [4].

1.2 Method of monitoring farmland using a drone.

After studying the existing technologies, the idea of full automation of not only monitoring the growth of cultivated plants and the degree of infestation of fields, but also the destruction of weeds in places of great localization was proposed.

Thus, the lethal device consists of the following components: drone, built-in camera with weed detection program, instruments for pollination and extraction of weed plants.

The method of weed control proposed by us consists of 4 main stages:

1) **Remote Video Surveillance:** The flying vehicle (drone) allows the farmer to monitor field debris at a distance, thus the drone will fly over the land at an altitude of less than 50 meters to take pictures as well as broadcast the screen online.

2) **Weed detection:** The camera attached to the drone performs broadcasting and detection functions.

Also, a written algorithm for color detection and detection integrated into the camera will make it possible to determine the localization of certain weeds by color.

3) **Herbicide pollination:** A container containing 5-10kg of herbicides will also be attached to the drone. Tubes will be attached along the main body, which are connected to the container and thus, having identified the weed plant, its dosed pollination will take place.

4) **Weed Extraction:** The drone will locate the weed and, upon receiving a signal from the farmer, perform a further extraction. A robotic arm attached to the drone on the underside of the main body will mechanically extract the weed.

1.3 Algorithm for detecting weeds.

One of the main details of the drone's work is the detection of weeds. This task is performed by the camera, to which the written algorithm will be connected [Appendix 1]. The program written in the Python programming language is able to distinguish such colors as: green, yellow and purple [Figure 1]. Thus, an unmanned aerial vehicle flying over the fields will be able to determine the localization of weeds and proceed to their further elimination.

Figure 1 Field model

1.4 Creating a 3D model.

In order to achieve the goal, the work was divided into several stages:

1. Selection of suitable elements and materials to create a layout of the drone's operation.
2. Making a diagram of an aircraft.
4. Assembling a model drone (camera, main body, container, LEGO MINDSTORMS).

5. Conducting testing of the finished model.

The assembly of the model began with the construction of the main body of the drone. It was assembled from LEGO parts and was supposed to act as a support for the entire structure.

Our next task was to create a robotic arm.

Figure 2 Drone model

It is also assembled from LEGO parts and connects to the LEGO MINDSTORMS hardware and software structure, to which code has been written allowing the user to arbitrarily control the robotic arm [Figure 2].

The next part of the model is the pollination device, which will be located along the propellers. Thereby, the pipes communicating with the tank will conduct herbicides to the taps due to artificially created pump and spray, detected weeds on signal [Figure 3].

Figure 3 Drone model

1.5 Conclusion and Conclusions

Most cultivated plants are constantly competing with weeds for nutrients and water, causing the use of herbicides in large quantities, which leads to herbicide aftereffects, decreased yield of subsequent crops and further disruption of the natural balance of nature.

The presented method of weed control is a more effective way to significantly reduce the number of weeds, reduce the cost of applying herbicides and obtain high quality crops.

Conclusions:

1. A weed detection program using small aircraft will significantly reduce the amount of herbicides used and reduce the cost of their application.
2. Reducing the amount of chemical spraying will reduce contamination of soils and groundwater with hazardous chemical compounds.
3. The small aircraft will allow you to spray at low altitudes, reducing the area of exposure to chemical compounds in natural ecosystems.

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